

A LOOK ON RE-USE THROUGH ART

Researching offices M127 and housing De Linde

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ono architectuur

Materials and energy have become increasingly valuable, making the importance of ecology as a theme more apparent. The support for hybrid building solutions combining new and re-use is growing rapidly. This requires adjusted thinking patterns in architectural design that entail the ability to repeatedly shift focus. Clear concepts make way for ever-varying thoughts on working with existing matter.

Various artists have paved the way by experimenting with this subject. Directly or subliminally, their works provide meaningful reasoning that gives rise to a different way of looking at existing heritage and its re-use. The influence can appear during the design process or in retrospection of the construction project. Leaving behind a purely visual comparison, we reference the metaphorical capacity of art, where societal themes are often driving forces that give rise to an unprecedented visual language. In picturing two projects, we rethink their relationship to art.

Gordon Matta-Clark
Francis Alÿs
Fischli & Weiss
Pierre Huyghe
Rachel Whiteread

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At M127, a '60s office building behaved hermetically towards its surroundings. At three precise locations, low stacked floors are cut away. The street façade is set backwards and floor fields are opened, making a double high city loggia in different sized voids. We take away part of the building and get more building in return.

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A letter from 1976 by Gordon Matta-Clark to a museum director can also be read as a text on re-use and connects very well with what we aim for. We re-use and punctually re-write the quote.

“My Our approach is to make do with whatever is possible while stretching our notions of the possible. † We use the urban fabric in its raw, ~~abandoned~~ state, transforming ~~unused~~ structures or spaces into revitalized areas. The space in its final next stage, is the ‘~~exhibition~~’ architecture and hopefully will have a life of its own within the community.”

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After cutting away, parts of the structure needed healing. The old concrete was locally strengthened with new concrete. Old and new concrete here exist next to each other in a bas-relief as a new time composition, with stronger chances for preserving its grey energy over time.

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In the facades some concrete columns are suddenly exposed to outside conditions. The conglomerate of old and new concrete is further enriched by an art integration project. The additional reinforcement cover is exaggerated in sculptural columns shaped by artist Philip Aguirre. A new public place is poured into the possibility of permanence.

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By adding new layers at M127 and at the same time revealing old ones, a building as a snapshot of different times appears. It is an outcome that leaves the idea of one conceptual path. With unfinished sympathy it doesn't want to close off the design nor define a finished architectural object.

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CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

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The '60s social housing building, De Linde, is defined by a rigid concrete structure and a specific concrete facade. Precast flat and ribbed panels, still in good condition, are stacked, resulting in a horizontal lining from a distance and an expressive assembly of elements and textures from close by.

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We propose to dismantle and stock the concrete panels on site, insulate the building and replace the panels. The added insulation makes the building thicken in both directions. We lack sufficient concrete panels to cover the full façade. The gaps thus created become the motive for an alternative padding.

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“Sometimes making something leads to nothing, sometimes making nothing leads to something.”
(Francis Alÿs)

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The action of dismantling and reassembling is required to change the view on the building and to keep it as it is. Finally, the materials move only a little bit. Small changes move mountains in our diligence and awareness of material consumption. The ‘not so new’ can be just fine.

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By not only relying on the work of artists, but also by integrating art in a not demarcated manner, cross-pollination is provoked when working on re-use projects. This leads to a pleasant interaction with the existing where everything pushes and pulls, sometimes congruent, sometimes contradictory, and where we can achieve unprecedented equilibria and scenes.

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CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

1. Illustration with names of referenced artists, ono architectuur
2. Mechelsesteenweg 127, Antwerp, before renovation, 2021, photo by David de Bruijn
3. Low stacked floors are cut away at three precise locations at ground floor, M127
4. Dismantling interior claddings at M127, 2021, photo by David de Bruijn
5. The adapted structure can house uses that weren't possible before, 2022, photo by David de Bruijn
6. *Office Baroque*, Gordon Matta-Clark, Antwerp, 1977
7. (Re-written) extract from a 'Letter from Gordon Matta-Clark to Florent Bex', 28.7.76, 1976
8. Isometric drawing of double-high void in M127, showcasing cut-through and new concrete
9. *Day's End*, Gordon Matta-Clark, New York, 1975
10. *House*, Rachel Whiteread, London, 1993
11. The old concrete is locally strengthened with new concrete at M127, 2024, photo by Filip Dujardin
12. The old concrete became the formwork of the new, M127, drawings by ono architectuur
13. Polystyrene moulds, Philip Aguirre, 2022, photo by David de Bruijn
14. Moulds and reinforcement nets around exposed concrete columns, photo by David de Bruijn
15. New cuts through the building are left in their raw state, 2023, photo by Filip Dujardin
16. *Timekeeper*, Pierre Huyghe, 1999
17. Adding new layers and revealing old ones at M127, 2023, photo by Filip Dujardin
18. Precast concrete ribbed and flat panels at De Linde, Tervuren, 2023, photo by Tom Beysen
19. De Linde as seen from the higher part of the village, Tervuren, 2023, photo by Tom Beysen
20. The stacking of ribbed and flat panels results in a horizontal articulation, photo by Tom Beysen
21. By insulating the building, we lack sufficient concrete panels to cover the full façade, digital drawing
22. Striped black and white tiling is inserted as traces of change, photomontage by ono architectuur
23. *Splitting*, Gordon Matta-Clark, New Jersey, 1974
24. *When Faith Moves Mountains*, Francis Alÿs, Lima, 2002
25. Dismantling and stocking the concrete panels on site before re-placing them, digital drawing
26. Finally, the materials move only a little bit (red = before, blue = after), digital drawing
27. *The Time at Our Disposal*, serie Equilibres, Fischli & Weiss, 1986

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